
Federated Learning for Energy Load Forecasting in Smart Homes

Aprendizaje Federado para la Previsión de la Carga Energética en Hogares Inteligentes

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ABSTRACT. The increasing complexity of residential energy consumption, driven by climate variability, smart devices, and distributed renewables, demands predictive solutions that are accurate, privacy-friendly, and adaptive. Therefore, forecasting energy demand is essential for suppliers to balance supply and demand in real time. In Latin America, these challenges are intensified by strict data protection laws, heterogeneous infrastructures, and dynamic consumption behaviors. In this context, traditional centralized load forecasting models have proven insufficient, as they lack the flexibility, transparency, and adaptability required for smart home energy management systems operating in distributed, non-stationary, and outage-prone conditions, limiting their usefulness for real-world decision-making. To address these limitations, we propose a generalized, adaptive, and explainable federated learning framework for residential load forecasting. The approach integrates data curation, preprocessing, federated clustering, and a forecasting model based on a temporal convolutional network with global attention, optimized through Bayesian optimization and augmented with feature attribution techniques, ensuring accurate and interpretable predictions. Preliminary results, validated with real-world datasets, show that the proposed system consistently improves accuracy in different scenarios, while providing interpretable information to support energy operators' decision-making. This work contributes to developing more resilient and sustainable energy infrastructures, aligned with the Sustainable Development Goals and the energy sector's digital transformation.

Keywords. *Energy forecasting, federated learning, interpretability, smart homes, sustainable energy management*

RESUMEN. La creciente complejidad del consumo energético residencial, impulsada por la variabilidad climática, los dispositivos inteligentes y las energías renovables distribuidas, exige soluciones predictivas precisas, respetuosas con la privacidad y adaptables. Por lo tanto, pronosticar la demanda energética es esencial para que los proveedores equilibren la oferta y la demanda en tiempo real. En Latinoamérica, estos desafíos se intensifican por las leyes de protección de datos, la heterogeneidad de las infraestructuras y los comportamientos dinámicos de consumo. En este contexto, los modelos tradicionales de pronóstico de carga centralizados resultan insuficientes, ya que carecen de flexibilidad, transparencia y adaptabilidad necesarias para los sistemas de gestión energética de hogares inteligentes que operan en condiciones distribuidas, no estacionarias y propensas a cortes de suministro, lo que limita su utilidad para la toma de decisiones en el mundo real. Para abordar estas limitaciones, proponemos un marco de aprendizaje federado generalizado, adaptable y explicable para el pronóstico de carga residencial. El enfoque integra curación de datos, preprocesamiento, agrupación en clústeres federados y un modelo de pronóstico basado en una red convolucional temporal con atención global, optimizado mediante optimización bayesiana e incrementado con técnicas de atribución de características garantizando predicciones precisas e interpretables. Los resultados preliminares, validados con conjuntos de datos reales, muestran que el sistema propuesto mejora de manera consistente la precisión en distintos escenarios, al tiempo que ofrece información interpretable para respaldar la toma de decisiones de los operadores energéticos. Este trabajo contribuye al desarrollo de infraestructuras energéticas más resilientes, inclusivas y sostenibles, alineadas con los Objetivos de Desarrollo Sostenible y la transformación digital del sector energético.

Palabras claves. *Aprendizaje federado, gestión sostenible, hogares inteligentes, interpretabilidad, pronóstico energético*

1. Introduction

Forecasting energy consumption in smart homes has become increasingly important due to the rise of Internet of Things devices, the need for efficient grid management, and the global push toward sustainability [1]. However, this task is becoming increasingly complex due to global population growth, rising demand for smart devices, climate variability, load flexibility, and the behavior of prosumers, who consume and generate energy, making electrical load estimation an increasingly complex challenge for energy systems [2]. This variability introduces uncertainty and complexity that traditional centralized forecasting models struggle to manage. While approaches based on Artificial Intelligence (AI) can capture nonlinear patterns, concerns about privacy, communication constraints, and the computational capacity of local devices limit centralized solutions [3]. Therefore, accurately, securely, and adaptively anticipating energy demand has become the key to designing resilient and energy infrastructures [4].

Federated Learning (FL) is emerging as a promising solution that allows multiple devices to collaborate on model training without sharing sensitive data, thus preserving privacy and adapting to diverse consumer behaviors [5]. However, FL still faces considerable challenges, such as communication overhead, high computational costs when incorporating additional variables, vulnerability to data heterogeneity, and difficulty ensuring fairness among clients with unequal resources [6]. These limitations make optimizing communication and model aggregation critical in smart home environments, where devices often operate with bandwidth and processing power constraints [7].

Given this scenario, a central question arises: How can a generalized and efficient FL framework be designed to accurately and sustainably predict residential energy consumption while preserving data privacy and adapting to heterogeneous environments? Based on this question, this work proposes a generalized and adaptive FL framework for residential load forecasting. It ensures scalability and adaptability while maintaining transparency and data privacy. Beyond its technical contributions, it delivers tangible social impact: utilities can access accurate forecasting models without handling sensitive consumer data, while households receive better tools to manage their energy efficiently. By aligning with the sustainability agenda SDG 7 (affordable and clean

energy), SDG 9 (innovation and resilient infrastructure), and SDG 13 (climate action), this approach contributes to laying the bases for a more sustainable and user-centric energy management system.

The remainder of the article is organized as follows: Section 2 presents related work, Section 3 describes the materials and methods, Section 4 presents some preliminary results and their discussion, and finally, Section 5 presents the conclusions.

2. Related Work

Energy demand forecasting has evolved from traditional statistical models to more advanced AI techniques [8]. While statistical methods work well in stationary environments, they often struggle to capture real-world data's complex, nonlinear relationships and multivariate dependencies [9]. Machine learning approaches greater predictive accuracy but can still fall short when faced with the highly variable and heterogeneous nature of actual household energy consumption, which changes over time and differs between households [10]. On the other hand, deep learning has demonstrated the ability to model complex temporal patterns, even when working with noisy or incomplete datasets. However, its reliance on centralized data collection creates computational burdens and raises serious privacy concerns [11]. Several studies have confirmed that FL is promising for load forecasting, effectively addressing the dual challenge of data privacy and heterogeneity in residential energy systems [12]. FL approaches are generally classified into three types: horizontal FL, where different households in other regions (with the same characteristics) collaborate; vertical FL, where different sets of attributes for the same users enable more comprehensive collaborative models; and federated transfer learning, which uses knowledge transfer to help new users or systems with little data [7].

From an architectural view, most home applications use a centralized FL configuration to achieve a practical balance between privacy, efficiency, and scalability, relying on a central server to manage model updates [13]. Alternatively, decentralized FL eliminates the central server and coordinates updates using peer-to-peer communication protocols, which can increase robustness and complexity in convergence and consistency [14]. Aggregation strategies such as FedSGD, FedAvg, and FedProx are crucial, as they directly influence the system's effectiveness in managing communication costs, data heterogeneity, and outliers [6], [15], [16].

The motivations for adopting FL in energy systems are clear: it ensures data privacy, reduces communication costs by transmitting only model parameters, distributes computational complexity across local devices, and improves scalability as the number of participants grows [2]. It also supports generalization through exposure to diverse contexts, mitigates data insufficiency in clients with limited records, and handles heterogeneous consumption patterns without centralizing sensitive information. In the energy sector, FL has already been applied to non-intrusive load monitoring, demand and generation forecasting, fault detection, and energy theft prevention, enhancing efficiency and security. Within residential forecasting, its integration with explainable models and clustering mechanisms opens new opportunities to design systems that are not only accurate and scalable, but also transparent and adaptable to evolving consumption behaviors, an essential requirement for smart home energy management and the transition toward resilient, sustainable grids [7], [17].

One example of the application of FL in domestic load forecasting is proposed by Połap et al. [4], who propose an architecture for smart homes that integrates edge computing, an LSTM with multi-head attention, decentralized learning, and blockchain with PoS, enabling secure and efficient energy demand forecasting. Lin et al. [18], who combine CNN with LSTM in a decentralized setup using asynchronous parameter updates to accelerate training and compensate for gradient delays. Xu et al. [19], employ FL with LSTM for short-term household load prediction, maintaining data locally in smart meters to reduce network load and enhance privacy. Rizwan et al. [20], integrate customer selection strategies to improve model accuracy, while Husnoo et al. [21], apply gradient quantization to defend against Byzantine attacks, achieving robustness without significant performance loss. Finally, Venkataramanan et al. [22], designed an FL-based framework for distributed energy resource prediction, validated with simulations.

Despite recent advances, structural gaps remain. Most frameworks still rely on static training structures, limiting adaptability to evolving consumption behaviors or sudden events such as energy crises. Additionally, residential data's noisy, non-stationary nature, shaped by weather, household composition, cultural habits, or device efficiency, makes generalization difficult without centralized aggregation. Finally, a critical gap is the limited explainability of current solutions, as predictive accuracy is prioritized over transparency.

Our work addresses these gaps by introducing an FL framework that integrates clustering-based personalization with a Temporal Convolutional Network enhanced by Global Attention (TCN-Attention) to achieve robust forecasting and adapt to evolving consumption patterns. This approach ensures scalability and adaptability while providing insights for smart home energy management in real-world environments.

3. Materials and Methods

3.1 Data Curation, Preprocessing, and Clustering

We used three public datasets from Germany [23], Switzerland [24], and northeastern Mexico [25], selected for their available features about household consumption, renewable generation, appliance use, and meteorological variables. A unified preprocessing pipeline was applied to harmonize the datasets. Missing values were handled through imputation (Equation 1), while anomalous peaks were corrected with interquartile-based filtering (Equation 2) to preserve the structural shape of load curves. All features were normalized to comparable scales (Equation 3), and time series were resampled to a standard 15-minute resolution, ensuring comparability across regions and reducing variability.

$$x_t^{(i)} = \begin{cases} x_t^{(i)}, & \text{if } x_t^{(i)} \text{ is observed} \\ \hat{x}_{match(t)}^{(i)}, & \text{if } \exists match(t) \\ median(x^{(i)}), & \text{otherwise} \end{cases} \quad (1)$$

$$x_t^{(i)} = \begin{cases} Q_1 - 1.5.IQR, & \text{if } x_t^{(i)} < Q_1 - 1.5.IQR \\ Q_3 + 1.5.IQR, & \text{if } x_t^{(i)} > Q_3 + 1.5.IQR \\ x_t^{(i)}, & \text{otherwise} \end{cases} \quad (2)$$

$$x_t^{(i,j)} = \frac{x_t^{(i,j)} - \min(x^{(j)})}{\max(x^{(j)}) - \min(x^{(j)})} \quad (3)$$

After preprocessing, we applied profile clustering to capture behavioral similarities among households. We identified groups with similar temporal consumption patterns using Dynamic Time Warping (DTW) to measure distances between load curves and Hierarchical Density-Based Spatial Clustering of Applications with Noise (HDBSCAN) for clustering. These clusters are the base for personalized federated models, enabling more efficient training, reducing heterogeneity, and improving generalization across diverse residential contexts.

Figure 1. FL approach implementation

3.2 FL pipeline implementation and TCN-Attention base forecasting model

In our proposal (see Figure 1), each household preprocesses its local smart meter data and participates in cluster-level training using the TCN-Attention model. The TCN captures long-range temporal dependencies through causal and dilated convolutions, while residual connections and normalization stabilize training and improve convergence. The attention mechanism is then applied to the TCN outputs to assign differentiated weights to input variables, highlighting the most relevant temporal patterns. To preserve privacy, raw consumption data never leaves the device. Instead, after several local training steps with Huber loss for robustness against outliers and non-stationary signals, clients transmit quantized model updates to the central server. The server aggregates these updates with a weighted FedAvg strategy [7], [26] and redistributes the refined global model back to the clients. This iterative cycle continues until convergence, ensuring scalability and fairness across heterogeneous clusters.

To enhance transparency, SHapley Additive exPlanations (SHAP) are integrated into the TCN-Attention outputs, quantifying the contribution of each input feature and providing interpretable insights beyond raw prediction accuracy [20]. As a result, the pipeline achieves accurate, explainable, and personalized load forecasting while supporting interoperability with grid-level energy management systems.

3.3 Bayesian Optimization for Load Forecasting

Algorithm 1 describes the procedure used to tune the hyperparameters of the TCN-Attention model. The process begins with an initial random exploration (lines 1–3), where $\{\theta_1, \theta_2, \dots, \theta_{n_{init}}\}$ is sampled from Θ and evaluated on \mathcal{L}_{val} . A Gaussian Process surrogate model is then fit to approximate the objective function (line 7), while α guides the selection of the next candidate by balancing exploration and exploitation (line 8). The candidate yielding the lowest validation loss is iteratively selected and used to update the surrogate, with the best configuration updated whenever a better solution is found (line 11). This loop continues until convergence, or the maximum number of iterations is reached (lines 13–14). The procedure is applied independently per cluster and typically converges in under 30 iterations.

Algorithm 1: Load Forecasting Model Optimization

Input:

Objective function $f(\theta)$: TCN-Attention loss under hyperparameters θ

Iteration Parameters:

n_{init} : number of random samples for optimization

n_{iter} : Maximum number of optimization iterations

Search Space Θ : Ranges of hyperparameters

Acquisition Function α : Guides exploration/exploitation θ

Validation loss \mathcal{L}_{val} : Evaluation metric

Output:

θ^* : Optimal hyperparameters of TCN-Attention model

1. Procedure:

2. Sample n_{init} $\{\theta_1, \theta_2, \dots, \theta_{n_{init}}\}$ from Θ

3. Evaluate $f(\theta_i)$ on TCN-Attention and $\mathcal{L}_{val}(\theta_i)$

4. Set initial $\theta_{best} = \arg \min \mathcal{L}_{val}(\theta_i)$

5. **for** iteration = 1 to n_{iter} **do**

6. Update surrogate model $g(\theta)$, using $f(\theta)$ to approximate the objective function

7. Use $\alpha(\theta|g)$ to select the next candidate hyperparameter

$$\theta_{next} = \arg \max \alpha(\theta|g)$$

8. Train and evaluate the TCN-Attention model on $f(\theta_{next})$.

9. Calculate $\mathcal{L}_{val}(\theta_{next})$

10. **if** $\mathcal{L}_{val}(\theta_{next}) < \mathcal{L}_{val}(\theta_{best})$ **then**

11. Update $\theta_{best} = \theta_{next}$

12. **if** convergence or n_{init} reached **then**

13. **break**

14. **return** $\theta^* = \theta_{best}$

3.4 Evaluation metrics

The evaluation relies on the Mean Absolute Error (MAE), which quantifies the average deviation of predictions, and the Root Mean Square Error (RMSE), which penalizes larger errors more heavily. These metrics emphasize accuracy and robustness, providing a good assessment of the model’s ability to generalize across time horizons and heterogeneous user profiles.

4. Results and Discussion

Figure 2 shows the different variables available in the datasets. The Swiss dataset captures seasonal aggregate trends, the German dataset includes fine-grained disaggregation, and the Mexican dataset reflects consumption under varying weather conditions—standardized preprocessing yields comparable multivariate time series despite structural differences, enabling joint clustering and federated model training.

Figure 2. Comparative Overview of Datasets

Figure 3 reports the RMSE and MAE across five client clusters, obtained through DTW-based consumption profile segmentation. The proposed TCN-Attention consistently outperforms baseline approaches (ARIMA, RNN, LSTM, and CNN), achieving lower prediction errors across all clusters. The improvements are particularly pronounced in high-variability groups (e.g., Cluster-1 and Cluster-5), where centralized and sequential models fail to capture non-stationary consumption patterns. These results confirm that incorporating cluster-level personalization within FL improves forecasting accuracy and robustness, ensuring better adaptation to heterogeneous household behaviors.

Figure 3. Comparison of forecasting performance across clusters

Figure 4 presents the importance of global features derived from SHAP values for the proposed federated TCN-Attention model. The results highlight that Solar generation is the most influential predictor of household energy demand, reflecting its strong correlation with consumption variability and renewable integration.

Figure 4. SHAP-Global attributions

This study represents an ongoing effort to consolidate an FL framework that balances accuracy, scalability, and interpretability in residential load forecasting. Current evaluations based on MAE and RMSE highlight the system’s capacity to generalize across heterogeneous households, while SHAP-based explanations ensure transparency in the decision process. The framework continues to evolve through refinements in clustering and aggregation strategies, aiming for adaptability under diverse operational conditions. Although our evaluation focused on datasets from Germany, Switzerland, and Mexico, the proposed framework is directly relevant to tropical regions such as Panama. In these contexts, energy demand is less driven by seasonal heating cycles and more by continuous cooling loads, coupled with heterogeneous infrastructures and frequent supply instabilities. Recent studies [27], [28] on energy consumption and forecasting in tropical environments underline the challenges of persistent cooling demand, high humidity, and weaker distribution infrastructures, all of which limit the applicability of traditional forecasting models. These insights reinforce the importance of designing federated frameworks capable of handling highly dynamic, non-stationary environments, making tropical climates a natural application field for our proposed approach. By combining profile clustering, personalized federated learning, and explainable feature attribution, our framework provides a robust pathway to extend forecasting reliability in such climates, where adaptability and interpretability are crucial for ensuring resilient energy management.

5. Conclusions

This work presented a generalized, adaptive, and explainable FL framework for residential energy forecasting, integrating data preprocessing, profile clustering, and a TCN-Attention architecture optimized

through Bayesian methods. The main contribution lies in combining scalability, privacy preservation, and interpretability, addressing critical gaps in centralized and federated approaches. The framework demonstrated advantages such as high predictive accuracy, noisy and heterogeneous data robustness, and transparent explanations supporting decision-making. The results directly apply to smart home energy management, grid-level coordination, and policy design, potentially strengthening resilience in Latin America and beyond, offering technical innovations and societal impact that foster progress in the energy sector.

CONFLICT OF INTEREST

The authors declare that they have no conflict of interest.

CONTRIBUTION AND APPROVAL BY THE AUTHORS

All authors affirm that we have read and approved the final version of this article.

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